

CODEN [USA]: IAJ PBB

ISSN : 2349-7750

**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**

SJIF Impact Factor: 7.187

Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Research Article

**COMPARATIVE STUDY ON SAFETY AND EFFICACY OF
VONOPRAZAN AND STANDARD PROTON PUMP INHIBITORS IN
PATIENTS WITH HELICOBACTER PYLORI INFECTION****Dr. A. Sujala, Gouti Akanksha, Nameera Khaton, Ruqsar Begum,
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Pharmacy Maha Vidyalaya, Hyderabad, India**Abstract:****Introduction:**

In this prospective study, the safety and efficacy of vonoprazan and standard proton pump inhibitors (PPIs) in the treatment of *Helicobacter pylori* infection are investigated. The study aims to compare the effects of these two acid-suppressing regimens on eradication rates, symptom relief, and patient-reported outcomes among individuals diagnosed with *H. pylori* infection. Vonoprazan and conventional PPIs are both widely used therapies as part of combination regimens for *H. pylori* eradication. The abstract will explore the differences in their mechanisms of acid suppression, pharmacokinetic properties, and potential side effects. Patient recruitment, study design, and outcome measures will be outlined, providing a comprehensive overview of the research methodology. Results will focus on eradication success rates, symptom improvement, patient satisfaction, and any adverse events observed during the study period. The abstract will conclude with implications for clinical practice and potential avenues for future research in this field.

Aim: To compare the Safety and Efficacy of Vonoprazan and Standard Proton pump inhibitors in *Helicobacter pylori* infection.

Objectives: Primary objective: To Compare the safety and efficacy of Vonoprazan and Standard Proton pump inhibitors in *Helicobacter pylori* infection.

Secondary objective: To check the Quality of life of patients taking Vonoprazan and Standard Proton pump inhibitors in *Helicobacter pylori* infection.

Methodology: The study is largely descriptive, and utilises data collected only under conditions of routine clinical care. All data collected/extracted is based solely on observations of disease management and treatment decisions made between the treating physicians and their patients.

Results And Discussion: In this study of 50 patients diagnosed with *Helicobacter pylori* infection, the majority were males aged 40–49 years. Patients were divided into two groups receiving either Vonoprazan-based or standard PPI-based triple therapy. Both groups showed clinical improvement, but the Vonoprazan group had more significant and complete symptom resolution. Post-treatment stool antigen tests confirmed 100% eradication in the Vonoprazan group, compared to only 76% in the PPI group. Quality of life scores, assessed through the Leeds Dyspepsia Questionnaire, revealed that all patients in the Vonoprazan group reported no dyspepsia, whereas most in the PPI group continued to experience some symptoms. These results demonstrate that Vonoprazan provided faster, more effective relief from symptoms and a higher eradication rate, likely due to its stronger and more sustained acid suppression.

Summary: The study concludes that Vonoprazan-based triple therapy is more effective than standard PPI-based therapy in the treatment of *H. pylori* infection. It led to complete symptom relief, higher eradication rates, and greater improvement in patient quality of life. Although both regimens were generally well tolerated, Vonoprazan demonstrated a superior safety and efficacy profile, making it a promising alternative to traditional PPI therapy for *H. pylori* eradication.

Key Words: *Helicobacter pylori*, Vonoprazan, Proton Pump Inhibitors, Eradication Therapy, Dyspepsia

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Please cite this article in press A. Sujala et al., Comparative Study On Safety And Efficacy Of Vonoprazan And Standard Proton Pump Inhibitors In Patients With *Helicobacter Pylori* Infection., *Indo Am. J. P. Sci*, 2026; 13(04).

INTRODUCTION:

Helicobacter pylori (*H. pylori*) is a spiral-shaped, gram-negative, microaerophilic bacterium that colonizes the gastric mucosa and is recognized as one of the most common chronic bacterial infections worldwide. It is estimated that more than 50% of the global population is infected with *H. pylori*, with higher prevalence rates observed in developing countries due to poor sanitation, overcrowding, and lower socioeconomic conditions. The bacterium is uniquely adapted to survive in the highly acidic environment of the stomach through the production of urease enzyme, which hydrolyzes urea into ammonia and carbon dioxide, thereby neutralizing gastric acid and facilitating colonization.

H. pylori infection plays a crucial role in the pathogenesis of several gastrointestinal disorders, including chronic gastritis, peptic ulcer disease (PUD), mucosa-associated lymphoid tissue (MALT) lymphoma, and gastric carcinoma. The organism has been classified as a Group I carcinogen by the World Health Organization due to its strong association with gastric malignancies. Although many infected individuals remain asymptomatic, a significant proportion develop dyspeptic symptoms such as epigastric pain,

The primary goal of treatment is the complete eradication of *H. pylori* infection, which leads to symptom relief, healing of ulcers, and prevention of recurrence and complications. Standard treatment regimens typically include a combination of antibiotics (such as amoxicillin and clarithromycin) along with acid-suppressing agents, predominantly proton pump inhibitors (PPIs). PPIs act by irreversibly inhibiting the gastric H⁺/K⁺-ATPase enzyme system, thereby reducing gastric acid secretion and creating a favorable environment for antibiotic activity.

Clinical studies have shown that vonoprazan-based regimens achieve higher eradication rates compared to conventional PPI-based therapies, particularly in patients with antibiotic-resistant *H. pylori* strains. Additionally, vonoprazan has been associated with improved symptom relief and better patient compliance due to its favorable pharmacokinetic and pharmacodynamic profile. Despite these advantages, comparative data on the safety and efficacy of vonoprazan versus standard PPIs in real-world clinical settings remain limited, especially in the Indian population.

Given the growing burden of *H. pylori* infection and the challenges associated with current treatment strategies, there is a need to explore more effective therapeutic alternatives. This study aims

to compare the safety and efficacy of vonoprazan and standard proton pump inhibitors in patients with *H. pylori* infection. The findings of this study may provide valuable insights into optimizing treatment regimens and improving clinical outcomes in affected patients.

➤ AIM & OBJECTIVES:**◆ AIM:**

To compare the Safety and Efficacy of Vonoprazan and Standard Proton pump inhibitors [Esomeprazole] in patients with *Helicobacter pylori* infection.

◆ OBJECTIVES:**1. PRIMARY OBJECTIVE:**

To Compare the safety and efficacy of Vonoprazan and Standard Proton pump inhibitors [Esomeprazole] in patients with *Helicobacter pylori* infection.

2. SECONDARY OBJECTIVE:

To check the Quality of life of patients taking Vonoprazan and Standard Proton pump inhibitors [Esomeprazole] in patients with *Helicobacter pylori* infection

METHODOLOGY:**❖ STUDY DESIGN:**

This is a Prospective Observational study.

❖ STUDY PERIOD:

The study was conducted for a period of 6 months.

❖ STUDY SITE:

The study was conducted at Department of Gastroenterology at Medicover Hospitals (Tertiary care hospital) Hitech City, Hyderabad.

❖ SAMPLE SIZE:

The study was performed with a sample size of 50 patients.

❖ ETHICAL APPROVAL:

The study was approved by the Institutional Ethical Committee of Medicover Hospitals, Hitech City, Hyderabad.

❖ STUDY CRITERIA:**➤ INCLUSION CRITERIA:**

- Patients aged >18 years.
- Patients with symptoms like Dyspepsia (i.e pain or discomfort centered in the upper abdomen) Bloating, Nausea,

- Vomiting, Loss of appetite.
- All genders.
- Patients who are willing to get enrolled in the study.
- Patients with endoscopic evidence with gastric ulcer and / or ulcer scar and duodenal ulcer and / or ulcer scar, Gastric lymphoma.
- Nodular / Atrophic gastritis

➤ **EXCLUSION CRITERIA:**

- A long-term NSAID treatment.
- History of allergy to drugs used in the study
- Intake of antibiotics, PPIs, corticosteroids within the last two weeks.
- History of gastric surgery such as partial and total gastrectomy.
- Pregnancy and lactating women.
- Clinically significant severe (cardiac, renal, hepatic) disease.

❖ **TOOLS USED;**

- Microsoft Excel, Microsoft Word, SPSS Inc.2014.

❖ **COLLECTION OF DATA:**

- The patient data is collected from the case sheets, Data collection forms and Leeds Dyspepsia questionnaire.

❖ **PLAN OF WORK:**

- Making protocol for the relevant study.
- Preparation of data collection forms, Patient consent forms, relevant Questionnaire.
- Ethical committee permission is taken for proceeding with the study.
- Taking patient data through case sheets and questionnaire.
- Identification of patient with H. pylori infection
- Taking patient's Demographic data and history of the patients with Vonoprazan and Standard PPI.
- Identifying the symptom duration (intermittent or persistent) and severity (mild, moderate, severe)
- Filling patient consent forms and patient profile forms through questionnaires and case sheets
- Patient is followed up for 2 months

- Post treatment Stool antigen test is performed and Symptoms are assessed using Validated questionnaire.
- Determining the clinical outcome of the patients having H. pylori infection and Interpretation of results.

RESULTS:

A prospective observational study was undertaken to assess the clinical outcomes, safety, and efficacy of vonoprazan and standard proton pump inhibitors (PPIs) in the treatment of Helicobacter pylori infection among patients seeking care in both out-patient and in-patient settings, alongside an investigation into prevailing treatment patterns. An extensive review of existing literature highlighted gastrointestinal symptoms such as epigastric pain, bloating, and nausea as the most prevalent manifestations of H. pylori infection. Notably, acid-suppressive therapy combined with appropriate antibiotics has emerged as the most efficacious therapeutic approach, leading to a substantial improvement in eradication rates and overall quality of life for affected individuals. This research study aimed to evaluate and compare the clinical outcomes and safety profile of vonoprazan-based therapy versus standard PPI-based therapy in treating H. pylori infection. Data were extensively collected from patients diagnosed with H. pylori infection presenting to the out-patients departments of Medicover Hospital, Hi-Tech City, Hyderabad.

Over the course of the study, a total of 50 patients representing a diverse spectrum of gastrointestinal symptoms were observed. This evaluation phase spanned from February 2025 to July 2025. Subsequently, the enrolled patients underwent interventions targeting their infection and associated symptoms. Out Of the 50 participants: Group 1 consisted of 25 patients who received Vonoprazan-based triple therapy. Group 2 consisted of 25 patients who received Standard PPI-based triple therapy. Consequently, the clinical outcomes and treatment analyses were based on the complete prospective cohort of 50 patients. The following results were observed from this study. Baseline characteristics of all patients are as follows (Age, Gender, Gastrointestinal symptoms, Diagnostic tests).

..Table 1:Distribution of patients according to age group

Comparison of mean of age between study group(N=50)

Parameter	Study group (Mean± SD)		P value
	Group 1 (N=25)	Group 2 (N=25)	
Age (in years)	39.44 ± 13.59	42.32 ± 14.44	0.471

Table 2: Distribution of patients according to gender

S.NO	AGE GROUP	NO. OF PATIENTS	PERCENTAGE (%)
1	21-29	11	22 %
2	30-39	12	24 %
3	40-49	13	26 %
4	50-59	9	18 %
5	60-69	3	6 %
6	70-80	2	4 %
	TOTAL	50	100 %

GENDER	NO. OF PATIENTS	PERCENTAGE (%)
Male	34	68 %
Female	16	32 %
Total	50	100 %

Distribution of patients according to age groups

Among 50 patients observed, their ages were categorized into 6 groups. From the table and graph, the age group 40-49 exhibited the highest patient count, comprising 13 (26%) individuals of the total. In contrast, the age groups 60-69, which included 3 (6%), and 70-80, which included 2 (4%), had the lowest overall presence of individuals. In addition, there

were 11 patients (22%) aged 21-29 years, 12 patients (24%) aged 30-39 years, and 9 patients (18%) aged 50-59 years age group.

Comparison of gender between study group (N=50)

Gender	Study Group		Chi square	P value
	Group 1 (N=25)	Group 2 (N=25)		
Male	16 (64%)	18 (72%)	0.368	0.544
Female	9 (36%)	7 (28%)		

Fig 10: Distribution of patients according to Gender

The table and accompanying pie chart present the distribution of patients with *Helicobacter pylori* infection according to gender. The data indicate that a majority of the cases occurred in males, comprising 34 patients (68%), whereas females constituted 16 patients (32%) of the study population.

Table 3: Distribution of patients according to GI symptoms

S.NO	GI SYMPTOMS	NO. OF PATIENTS	PERCENTAGE (%)
1	Epigastric pain	25	22.3%
2	Abdominal pain	12	10.7%
3	Abdominal bloating	25	22.3%
4	Halitosis	1	0.89%
5	Burning sensation	2	1.78%
6	Belching	19	16.96%
7	Nausea	8	7.14%
8	Vomiting	6	5.35%
9	Constipation	7	6.25%
10	Regurgitation	2	1.78%
11	Acid reflux	3	2.67%
12	Loose stool	1	0.89%
13	Malena	1	0.9%

Comparison of Chief Complaints between study group (N=50)

Chief Complaints	Study Group		P value
	Group 1 (N=25)	Group 2 (N=25)	
Epigastric Pain			
Yes	6 (24%)	6 (24%)	1.000
No	19 (76%)	19 (76%)	
Abdominal Pain			
Yes	3 (12%)	0 (0%)	*
No	22 (88%)	25 (100%)	
Abdominal Bloating			
Yes	5 (20%)	1 (4%)	0.189
No	20 (80%)	24 (96%)	
Epigastric Burning			
Yes	1 (4%)	0 (0%)	*
No	24 (96%)	25 (100%)	
Halitosis			
Yes	1 (4%)	0 (0%)	
No	24 (96%)	25 (100%)	
Belching			
Yes	3 (12%)	4 (16%)	1.000
No	22 (88%)	21 (84%)	
Acid Reflux			
Yes	2 (8%)	0 (0%)	*
No	23 (92%)	25 (100%)	
Dyspepsia Symptoms			
Yes	2 (8%)	11 (44%)	0.004
No	23 (92%)	14 (56%)	
Nausea			
Yes	4 (16%)	4 (16%)	1.000
No	21 (84%)	21 (84%)	
Vomiting			
Yes	2 (8%)	4 (16%)	0.667
No	23 (92%)	21 (84%)	
Bloating			
Yes	9 (36%)	4 (16%)	0.107
No	16 (64%)	21 (84%)	
Constipation			
Yes	4 (16%)	3 (12%)	1.000
No	21 (84%)	22 (88%)	
Regurgitation			
Yes	1 (4%)	0 (0%)	*
No	24 (96%)	25 (100%)	

*No statistical test was applied- due to '0' subjects in the cells

Fig 11: Distribution of patients according to GI symptoms

Table 3 and the accompanying graph illustrate the distribution of patients based on gastrointestinal (GI) symptoms. Epigastric pain and abdominal bloating were the most frequently reported symptoms, each affecting 25 patients (22.3%). Nausea was reported by 19 patients (16.96%), followed by abdominal pain in 12 patients (10.7%). Other symptoms included constipation (6.25%), vomiting (5.35%), and acid reflux (2.67%). Less common symptoms such as regurgitation and burning sensation were each observed in 2 patients (1.78%). Rare symptoms, including halitosis, loose stool, and malena, were each reported by a single patient (<1%).

Table 4: Distribution of patients according to Rapid Urease Test

S.NO	RUT	NO. OF PATIENTS	PERCENTAGE (%)
1	Positive	29	58%
2	Negative	21	42%
	TOTAL	50	100%

Comparison of rapid urease test(rut) between study group (N=50)

Rapid urease test (RUT)	Study Group		Chi square	P value
	Group 1 (N=25)	Group 2 (N=25)		
Negative	9 (36%)	12 (48%)	0.739	0.390

Fig 12: Distribution of patients according to Rapid Urease Test

Table 4 and accompanying figure shows the distribution of patients based on the results of the Rapid Urease Test (RUT). Out of a total of 50 patients, 29 patients (58%) tested positive for *H. pylori* infection, while 21 patients (42%) tested negative. The accompanying chart illustrates the proportion of positive and negative cases, highlighting that the majority of patients had a positive RUT result.

Table 5: Distribution of patients based on Treatment given

S.NO.	TREATMENT	NO. OF PATIENTS	PERCENTAGE
1	VONOPRAZAN	25	50%
2	STANDARD PPI	25	50%
	TOTAL	50	100%

Fig 13: Distribution of patients according to Treatment given

The table and graph above illustrate the distribution of patients based on the treatment regimen administered. The first group, comprising 25 patients (50%), received Vonoprazan at a daily dose of 20 mg twice daily. The second group, also consisting of 25 patients (50%), was treated with Standard PPI at a total daily dose of 40 mg, administered twice daily.

Table 6: Distribution of patients according to Dyspepsia symptoms (pre treatment)

S.NO	DYSPEPSIA SYMPTOMS	PRE TREATMENT			
		VONOPRAZAN		STD PPI	
		No. of patients	Percentage	No. of patients	Percentage
1	Indigestion	24	28.23%	22	30.98%
2	Regurgitation	22	25.88%	13	18.30%
3	Heartburn	21	24.70%	16	22.53%
4	Nausea	18	21.17%	20	28.16%

Fig 14: Distribution of patients according to Dyspepsia symptoms (pre treatment)

Table 6 and the accompanying graph illustrate the distribution of patients based on dyspepsia symptoms prior to treatment in the Vonoprazan and Standard PPI groups. Indigestion was the most frequently reported symptom in both groups, affecting 24 patients (28.23%) in the Vonoprazan group and 22 patients (30.98%) in the Standard PPI group. Regurgitation and heartburn were reported more commonly in the Vonoprazan group, with 22 (25.88%) and 21 patients (24.70%) respectively, compared to 13 (18.30%) and 16 patients (22.53%) in the Standard PPI group. Nausea was slightly more prevalent in the Standard PPI group, affecting 20 patients (28.16%) compared to 18 (21.17%) in the Vonoprazan group.

Table 7: Distribution of patients according to Dyspepsia symptoms (post treatment)

S.NO	DYSPEPSIA SYMPTOMS	POST TREATMENT			
		VONOPRAZAN		STD PPI	
		No. of patients	Percentage	No. of patients	Percentage
1	Indigestion	3	33.33%	4	25%
2	Regurgitation	2	22.22%	2	20.83%
3	Heartburn	2	22.22%	5	29.16%
4	Nausea	2	22.22%	5	25%

Fig 15: Distribution of patients according to Dyspepsia symptoms (post treatment)

Table 15 and the accompanying graph illustrate the distribution of patients based on dyspepsia symptoms after treatment. Indigestion was the most frequently reported symptom, affecting 3 patients (33.33%) in the Vonoprazan group and 4 patients (25%) in the Standard PPI group. Heartburn and nausea were each reported by 2 patients (22.22%) receiving Vonoprazan, while 5 patients in the Standard PPI group reported heartburn (29.16%) and nausea (25%). Regurgitation was noted by 2 patients (22.22%) in the Vonoprazan group and 2 patients (20.83%) in the Standard PPI group.

The graph highlights the overall reduction in symptom prevalence following treatment in both groups compared to baseline values.

Table 8: Distribution of patients according to Stool Antigen Test H. pylori (pre treatment)

S.NO	Stool antigen test for H. pylori	No. of patients	
		Vonoprazan	Standard PPI
1	Detected	0	6
2	Not Detected	25	19

Comparison of stool antigen test pretreatment between study group (N=100)

Stool Antigen Test Pre-Treatment	Study Group		Chi square	P value
	Group 1 (N=25)	Group 2 (N=25)		
Detected	25 (50%)	25 (50%)	0.000	1.000

Fig 16: Distribution of patients according to Stool Antigen Test H. pylori (pre treatment)

Table 8 and the accompanying graph illustrate the distribution of patients based on the results of the Stool Antigen Test for H. pylori before treatment. In both the Vonoprazan and Standard PPI groups, H. pylori infection was detected in all 25 patients (100%), while none of the patients tested negative

Table 9: Distribution of patients according to Stool Antigen Test H. pylori (post treatment)

S.NO	Stool antigen test for H. pylori	No. of patients	
		Vonoprazan	Standard PPI
1	Detected	25	25
2	Not Detected	0	0

Fig 17: Distribution of patients according to Stool Antigen Test H. pylori (post treatment)

Table 9 and the accompanying graph illustrate the distribution of patients according to the Stool Antigen Test for H. pylori after treatment. In the Vonoprazan group, H. pylori antigen was not detected in 25 patients, indicating successful eradication in all cases, with 0 patients remaining positive after therapy.

In the Standard PPI group, H. pylori antigen was not detected in 19 patients, while 6 patients continued to show positive results, suggesting incomplete eradication in a proportion of cases.

The graph clearly demonstrates that Vonoprazan achieved a higher eradication rate compared to Standard PPI

Comparison of mean of pre and post treatment various parameters between study group (N=50)

Parameter	Study group (Mean± SD)		P value
	Group 1 (N=25)	Group 2 (N=25)	
Indigestion pre-treatment	4.76 ± 1.85	5.08 ± 1.98	0.558
Heartburn pre-treatment	4.64 ± 2.33	3.04 ± 2.46	0.022
Regurgitation pre-treatment	4.72 ± 2.05	2.52 ± 2.57	0.002
Nausea pre-treatment	4 ± 2.72	4.2 ± 2.47	0.787
Total score pre-treatment	18.12 ± 3.41	14.84 ± 2.73	<0.001
Indigestion post-treatment	0 ± 0	0.24 ± 0.44	0.008
Heartburn post-treatment	0 ± 0	0.28 ± 0.46	0.004
Regurgitation post-treatment	0 ± 0	0.2 ± 0.41	0.018
Nausea post-treatment	0 ± 0	0.24 ± 0.44	0.008
Total score post-treatment	0 ± 0	0.96 ± 0.45	<0.001

Table: Comparison of between the two groups at different follow-up time periods (N=50)

	Regurgitation Posttreatment		Mann Whitney U test (P value)
	Group 1 (N=25)	Group 2 (N=25)	
Indigestion pre-treatment (n=50)	5 (4,6.5)	5 (4.5,6.5)	0.320
Heartburn pre-treatment (n=50)	5 (4,6.5)	4 (0,5)	0.017
Regurgitation pre-treatment (n=50)	5 (4,6)	3 (0,5)	0.003
Nausea pre-treatment (n=50)	5 (0,6)	5 (3,6)	0.921
Total score pre-treatment (n=50)	17 (16,20)	16 (12.5,16.5)	0.001
Indigestion post-treatment (n=50)	0 (0,0)	0 (0,0.5)	0.010
Heartburn post-treatment (n=50)	0 (0,0)	0 (0,1)	0.005
Regurgitation post-treatment (n=50)	0 (0,0)	0 (0,0)	0.020
Nausea post-treatment (n=50)	0 (0,0)	0 (0,0.5)	0.010
Total score post-treatment (n=50)	0 (0,0)	1 (1,1)	<0.001

CONCLUSION:

In this study, an effective treatment for Helicobacter pylori infection with maximum eradication rates was evaluated. This prospective, observational study compared the safety and efficacy of Vonoprazan-based triple therapy with standard Proton Pump Inhibitor (PPI)-based triple therapy. A total of 50 patients diagnosed with H. pylori infection were included and randomly divided into two groups. Group I comprised 25 patients who received Vonoprazan 20 mg twice daily along with amoxicillin and clarithromycin, while Group II included 25 patients who received a standard PPI (Esomeprazole) twice daily with the same antibiotics. Post-treatment evaluation was done using stool antigen tests and the Leeds Dyspepsia Questionnaire which revealed that both

groups showed statistically significant improvement in symptoms and bacterial eradication. However, the Vonoprazan group achieved higher eradication rate, compared to that of standard PPI group. Additionally, the Vonoprazan group demonstrated slightly better symptom relief and patient tolerance. The results indicate that Vonoprazan-based triple therapy is a highly effective and well-tolerated regimen for the eradication of Helicobacter pylori infection.

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